

STRATEGIES OF IMPROVING RECEPTIVE SKILLS

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Abstract. *Learning structures and methods vary, but they typically lead to positive outcomes when they enhance listening skills. Similar to language and cognitive components, second language acquisition involves various factors that affect language learning and development. This study highlights key factors identified through scientific research. Stimulating activities captivate learners and increase the efficiency of their efforts. Activities that engage interest are more likely to generate positive emotions, making tasks feel easier, less demanding, and requiring higher concentration.*

Keywords: *receptive skills, reading skills, listening skills, activities.*

Introduction

In a 2020 speech, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev of Uzbekistan emphasized that "Each graduate must be fluent in at least two foreign languages" and announced the creation of the Agency for the Promotion of the Study of Foreign Languages. This move comes in response to the growing demand for foreign language education, particularly English, amidst globalization. In his speech, Mirziyoyev also highlighted the vital role of education in addressing the world's challenges, fostering stability, and promoting tolerance. Language is not only essential for communication but also for learning, as without effective language skills, one cannot fully understand subjects or communicate ideas clearly. English, being the primary foreign language taught in Uzbekistan, plays a central role in the educational process. To enhance learners' language proficiency, EFL (English as a Foreign Language) teachers must implement effective strategies.

Listening is essential for effective communication, and without strong listening skills, messages are easily misinterpreted. Most children naturally develop good listening skills, and it is important to create purposeful and engaging activities to help students further refine these skills. Surprising students can ignite curiosity and stimulate conversation, prompting them to explore ideas and actively participate in discussions.

Receptive skills, which include listening and reading, do not require learners to produce language but focus on understanding and interpreting it. These skills are considered "passive" compared to productive skills like speaking and writing. In language learning, receptive skills often come first, followed by the development of productive skills. The relationship between these two sets of skills is complex but complementary, as the development of one typically supports the growth of the other. For example, improving reading skills can positively influence writing abilities.

Receptive skills help learners process and extract meaning from spoken or written discourse. While there are similarities in how we process both reading and listening, there are also notable differences, which must be addressed when teaching these skills. Both reading and listening rely on prior knowledge, which is referred to as schema. This prior knowledge helps learners anticipate and make sense of the information they encounter. Whether reading a book, listening to a news broadcast, or participating in a conversation, schema allows learners to quickly recognize patterns and understand content more effectively. For instance, when reading a

letter, the reader's schema helps them identify whether the text is an invitation, a rejection letter, or a job offer.

Understanding how we read and listen is crucial for developing these skills. When we read or listen, we employ both "top-down" and "bottom-up" processes. Top-down processing involves making general predictions about a text based on prior knowledge, while bottom-up processing focuses on decoding individual words and phrases to build meaning. Both processes interact and complement each other during reading and listening, as effective comprehension often requires balancing both approaches.

Conclusion

The advancement of new technologies has opened up new opportunities for teaching listening skills, especially for younger learners. Research into cognitive processes related to listening has deepened our understanding of the challenges involved, particularly in a second language (L2). Listening in L2 is often perceived as more difficult, leading to anxiety that can hinder learners' performance. However, this challenge can be overcome by focusing on the different stages of comprehension (perception, parsing, and utilization). Teachers can help by promoting the use of both bottom-up and top-down cognitive strategies to overcome these difficulties. Additionally, incorporating metacognitive strategies into language courses can help learners become more aware of listening strategies, fostering autonomy and improving their listening skills.

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